

BEX IMAGING: A NEW APPROACH FOR MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION IN THE SEM.

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Introduction: Non-destructive characterization of rare and precious extraterrestrial matter, such as meteorite fragments, lunar Apollo samples, and 'dust' grains from sample return missions (e.g. Stardust; Hayabusa; Asteroid Bennu) is a delicate mission in itself. Extraterrestrial samples returning to Earth are subject to issues of preservation, terrestrial contamination, and permanent alterations/damage during laboratory investigations. Extraterrestrial sample need to be kept as pristine as possible; typically small quantities of variably sized (sub-micrometre to hundred of micrometre), chemically heterogeneous and electrically non-conductive fragments of rock debris.

One widely used and established non-destructive technique for extraterrestrial sample characterization is Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) in the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The EDS technique has several advantages, including a relatively simple analytical setup, the ability to auto-ID unknown elements which means no prior knowledge of the sample is required, high spatial and analytical resolution, and the ability to acquire elemental distributions maps. All of this makes EDS ideal for characterization of chemically variable particles. Despite these advantages it still holds true that EDS needs enough X-ray signal for accurate element abundance detection and quantification, which on older-generation EDS systems was achieved by either long acquisition times, or high-current/high energy electron beam settings. Neither option is recommended for precious extraterrestrial samples, because long acquisition times mean prolonged beam exposures on the sample surface causing problems with sample drift and electrical charging, whereas high-current/high energy beam settings mean large interaction volumes producing inaccurate quantification, and potential beam damage to the sample. On older analytical systems, these conditions would realistically limit the applicability of EDS to spot analysis and low-count chemical maps. Furthermore, EDS, being a surface technique, ideally requires a flat and polished samples whereas extraterrestrial dust particles tend to be irregular and contain topography. Non-conductive particles also produce electric charging effects that require either deposition of a metallic coating, or analysis under variable pressure SEM conditions. From the above, it is clear that analysis of precious extraterrestrial powders with EDS is challenging and does not always provide the desired results.

Oxford Instruments has recently introduced Unity, a new first of its kind detector, that drastically

reduced most of the issues related to this type of samples, thus unlocking the full potential for characterization of extraterrestrial dust. Oxford Instruments' Unity is a Backscatter Electron and X-ray imaging (BEX) detector. The first imaging detector that collects both, backscatter electron (BSE) and EDS images simultaneously. Unity has been engineered to maximise signal collection of both BSE and X-rays allowing full characterization of samples at live microscope imaging refresh rates, redefining *state-of-the-art* Live Chemical Imaging.

Unlike "conventional" EDS detectors that are positioned in the SEM at an angle of about 35° to the sample surface, Unity is flat beneath the pole piece, unlocking a very large solid angle and EDS elemental maps of 3D particles without shadowing. Unity can also be operated at variable pressure, removing the need for metallic coating while still acquiring robust datasets.

Methods: To demonstrate the benefits of Oxford Instruments new solution for a comprehensive, non-destructive characterization of precious extraterrestrial samples, a soil dust sample was analysed in the SEM, using Unity and an Ultim Max Infinity 170 EDS detector simultaneously. This soil dust sample was used as a dummy representing extraterrestrial material. The particles were stuck to a C-adhesive stub and placed in a field emission-SEM. Signals from both detectors were acquired simultaneously. Working conditions were 15 kV, 1.2 nA and 8.5 mm working distance. SE, BSE and EDS images were acquired simultaneously at live microscope imaging refresh rates, producing a comprehensive dataset of images and elemental distribution maps. Full sample characterization of the 450 mm² sample area was acquired in 10 to 45 minutes depending on image resolution. BSE and EDS maps were then displayed in overlaid mode to highlight compositional differences not visible with greyscale imaging alone.

Results: A comprehensive imaging and chemical dataset was acquired on a soil sample using the new BEX imaging technique. Results of this analysis are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Stitched large area scan of soil dust sample. The image shows the BSE signal of Unity. Acquisition time of such a ~450 mm² sample can take between 10 and 30 minutes.

Figure 2: Single BEX image of the large area scan shown in figure 1. The BEX technique reveals the chemical variations within the dust particles without being compromised by conventional experimental artifacts like shadowing. Field of view ca. 1.2 mm. Red: aluminium; Green: iron; Blue: silicon; Yellow: Calcium; Teal: titanium.

Discussion: EDS has been a versatile and powerful microanalytical tool for decades, yet some categories of materials, such as delicate samples of extraterrestrial powder from sample return missions, still prove challenging to analyse with “conventional” EDS solutions. This is because conventional EDS detectors perform best on flat, polished and electrically conductive samples that are not beam-sensitive. Unfortunately, the typical extraterrestrial sample is likely to be the exact opposite: a few micrograms of rock fragments of variable sizes and shapes, non-conductive, chemically heterogeneous and beam sensitive. Here we present Oxford Instruments latest developments in materials characterization and pro-

pose a solution and analytical workflow that is perfectly suited to investigate challenging extraterrestrial samples and unlocking the full potential of analytical electron microscopy.

The solution uses the Oxford Instruments BEX imaging detector Unity that sits flat under the pole piece for simultaneous chemical and backscatter imaging. This solution offers important advantages compared to conventional EDS and imaging techniques. Firstly, the possibility to perform *state-of-the-art* Live Chemical Imaging. Navigation on the sample is now no longer limited to greyscale secondary electron or BSE imaging, as EDS-based chemical maps are also acquired simultaneously, creating coloured images with real chemical distribution information. Secondly, BEX resolves a typical drawback of conventional EDS, which is the analysis of rough surfaces without introducing shadowing artifacts. The resulting chemical maps acquired with BEX give equal illumination of 3D particles, eliminating the need for polished samples. The whole sample fully characterized morphologically and chemically, in short acquisition times also makes efficient use of the analytical equipment. Finally, this solution provides for a large comprehensive dataset that can be fully studied offline reducing user time on the scientific equipment. Post processing and chemical analysis can be conducted without compromises on the collected dataset.